

DUAL-SCALE MODELLING OF FLOW THROUGH NON-UNIFORM BI-DIRECTIONAL FABRICS

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SUMMARY: In this study, permeability variations in bi-directional textile fabrics are described by non-uniformities in the fabric structure. Determination of the local permeability of a reinforcement textile is based on simulation of resin flow at the unit cell level (meso-scale). For the simulations, a detailed geometrical model of the three-dimensional unit cell configuration is spatially discretised and porosity and permeability are locally averaged on the grid. The calculated permeability values of the unit cell suggest that stochastic variation of the fibre configuration results in normally distributed permeability values. To determine the global fill time and the global flow patterns, the resin flow is simulated at the component level (macro-scale). Stochastic variations in the local permeability are described by continuous random fields. Simulation results indicate that the global permeability variations decrease with decreasing dimensions of the fabric inhomogeneities and with increasing mould dimensions.

KEYWORDS: Liquid Composites Moulding, flow simulation, textile permeability, non-uniformity

INTRODUCTION

In Liquid Composites Moulding (LCM) processes, the impregnation of the textile reinforcement structure with liquid resin is determined by the textile permeability, which in general shows high variations due to non-uniformities of the textile structure. Due to these variations, the mould filling patterns and injection times in LCM processing of actual components are hard to predict. The product quality and the production cycle time may be affected. With regard to the robust manufacture of composite components applying LCM processes, this study aims to model the effect of random variations in the fabric architecture on the global textile permeability, which is a prerequisite for the prediction of probable outcomes of resin injections. Two concurrent approaches for permeability modelling and flow simulation exist: While description of the local flow behaviour is based on detailed geometrical information on the unit cell, formulation of the global flow problem relies on estimation of the local variations in the fabric structure over the component dimensions.

MESO-SCALE MODELLING

Grid Average Method

In the Grid Average (GA) method, a textile geometric model is generated automatically from the “TexGen” software (University of Nottingham, [1]). The flow domain is discretised into a regular grid of cubes. The permeability \mathbf{K} is calculated for each cube by thickness-weighted averaging of the properties of the layers contained within the cube according to

$$\mathbf{K} = \frac{1}{h_e} \sum_{i=1}^N h_i \mathbf{K}_i \quad (1)$$

h_e is the edge length of the cube, h_i and \mathbf{K}_i are the thicknesses and the permeabilities of the N layers contained within the cube. For a layer representing a channel with height h between two fibre tows, the equivalent permeability, derived from analysis of flow between two flat plates, is $h^2/12$. For a layer representing porous tow, the permeability is calculated from the porosity and geometry parameters according to Gebart [2]. On the four sides of the computational domain, periodic pressure boundary conditions are imposed. On the top and bottom, the normal flow velocity component is zero, as it is assumed that there is no fluid exchange. For saturated flow, the pressure field on the flow domain is calculated based on a finite differences scheme. According to Darcy’s law, the effective permeability of the fibre configuration in flow direction is determined from the resulting flow rate. The flow problem can be further simplified by projecting the porosity and permeability of the three-dimensional fabric model onto a two-dimensional grid (Fig. 1C). For the two-dimensional formulation of the flow problem, the permeability is calculated in analogy to the three-dimensional case.

Fig. 1: Grid Average method for a 2x2 twill weave fabric; A: calculated fibre volume fraction; B: fibre tows; C: projection of the fibre volume fraction onto a 2D grid

Permeability Calculation

The permeability was calculated for the model of a 2x2 twill weave fabric with fibre orientations of $\pm 45^\circ$ relative to the main flow direction. The fibre tows are assumed to have an elliptical cross section with a width of 0.8 mm and height of 0.2 mm. The fibre volume fraction within the tows is 50 %, giving tow permeabilities of $4.38 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$ (axial) and $8.07 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2$ (transverse) for quadratic packing of the fibres [2]. The dimensions of the flow domain, which contains one unit cell of the fabric, are 4.0 mm \times 4.0 mm \times 0.6 mm.

To study the effect of fabric shear on the permeability, simulations with angles between the fibre axes and the flow direction ranging from $\pm 30^\circ$ to $\pm 60^\circ$ were performed. In addition, statistical variations were applied implementing a Monte-Carlo approach, which implies randomly moving the crossover points of the tows such that the resulting fibre spacing is normally distributed with a standard deviation of 14 %. Examples for the 100 random cases that were modelled and solved using the two-dimensional GA approach with a resolution of 41×41 nodes are shown in Fig. 2. While the tow paths vary randomly within the computational domain, the configuration on the boundaries is consistent with periodic boundary conditions.

Fig. 2: Examples of fibre configurations with statistical variations solved by the GA method; the computational domains are shaded

Results

For flow parallel to the x -axis of the computational domain (Fig. 1), the permeability values K_x predicted using the GA approach are plotted in Fig. 3 for different angles between the main flow direction and the fibre axes. The trends predicted by 2D and 3D GA analyses are similar with only a small difference between the respective values. Starting from the initial configuration at $\pm 45^\circ$, the predicted permeability increases with decreasing angles until a maximum value is reached at about $\pm 37.5^\circ$. K_x then decreases towards smaller angles. For increasing angles, on the other hand, the values of K_x decrease continuously. This trend agrees with the experimental observations reported by Smith et al. [3] for various bi-directional fabrics. The results can be explained by two concurrent mechanisms induced by fabric shear, the reorientation of the fibres relative to the flow direction and the reduction of porosity. Since parallel to the tow axis the permeability of a fibre tow is higher than transverse to the tow axis, the fabric permeability is increased for angles below $\pm 45^\circ$ (rotation of tows towards flow direction) and decreased for angles higher than $\pm 45^\circ$ (rotation away from flow direction). For fabric shear in either direction, the fibre volume fraction is increased and the permeability decreased. Of both effects, flow inhibition due to increased fibre volume fraction becomes dominant as the fibre angle drops below $\pm 40^\circ$, and the permeability decreases. For angles higher than $\pm 45^\circ$, the combined effects of increased fibre volume fraction and reorientation of fibres away from the direction of flow significantly reduce the permeability.

Fig. 3: Predicted permeability values for flow along the x-axis as a function of the angles of fibre orientations

For stochastic variations in the fibre configuration, Fig. 4 shows the predicted permeability distribution, which has a mean value of $3.86 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$ and a standard deviation of $0.12 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$. The simulated data correlate well with a normal distribution. The relative standard deviation (standard deviation / mean value) is 3.0 %. Pan et al. [4] report a relative standard deviation of 13.1 % for woven fabrics. In general, a narrow distribution may be expected here as only one layer of fabric was modelled. Several layers are normally used in experiments, and Hoes et al. [5] showed that nesting of layers has a strong influence on the scatter in permeability values. The model for this study was also constrained in terms of fibre configuration in order to maintain a repetitive unit cell.

Fig. 4: Predicted distribution of K_x for statistical variations of the fabric structure; histogram and corresponding normal distribution; the correlation coefficient is 0.992

MACRO-SCALE MODELLING

Local Permeability Distributions

The local fibre volume fraction of a bi-directional non-crimp fabric is determined based on considerations for the textile unit cell, which is shown in Fig. 5. The fibre volume within the unit cell is given by the fibre tow cross-section, the fibre tow length and the fibre volume fraction within the fibre tows V_{fibre} . The value of V_{fibre} is estimated by $V_{fmax} = 0.6$, which is achieved in composite components produced by conventional manufacturing methods. The fibre tows are assumed to have an approximately elliptical cross-section with semi-major axis R_p , which lies in the fabric plane, and semi-minor axis R_t , which is oriented perpendicular to the fabric plane. The volume of the unit cell corresponds to the product of the area, included by the fibre tow axes a and b , and the height of the cell, which is identified with the value $4R_t$. Thus, the fibre volume fraction is

$$V_f = \frac{V_{fibre}}{V} = \frac{\pi R_p R_t (a+b) V_{fmax}}{4abR_t} = \frac{\pi R_p (a+b) V_{fmax}}{4ab} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 5: Unit cell of a bi-directional non-crimp fabric

Fig. 6: Distances between the axes of wavy fibre tows in non-uniform fabrics

The distances a and b between fibre tows in non-uniform bi-directional non-crimp fabrics (Fig. 6) are described by continuous random fields formulated in spectral expansions as suggested by Ghanem and Dham [6]. The distances are given by

$$a - 2R_p = (a_0 - 2R_p) \left(1 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} w_i(x) w_i(y) \right) \quad (3)$$

and

$$b - 2R_p = (b_0 - 2R_p) \left(1 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} w_i(x) w_i(y) \right) \quad (4)$$

implementing the functions

$$w_i(x) = \sin(\omega_{ai} x + \varphi_{ai}) \quad (5)$$

and

$$w_i(y) = \sin(\omega_{bi} y + \varphi_{bi}) \quad (6)$$

with the random frequencies ω_{ai} , ω_{bi} and phases φ_{ai} , φ_{bi} . a_0 and b_0 are the average distances between the fibre tow axes.

Assuming that the properties in both fibre directions are identical, the estimation

$$\omega_{\max} = \frac{\tan \sigma_\alpha}{a_0 - 2R_p} \quad (7)$$

for the maximum random frequency was derived [7]. The values of ω_{\max} are determined from the fibre angle variations, which are described by the standard deviation σ_α of the angle distribution, and the geometry parameters a_0 and R_p , which are related to the structure of actual fabrics. From the functions describing the fibre tow distances, continuous distributions of the local fibre volume fraction (Fig. 7) are calculated according to Eqn. 2. Local permeability values

$$K_1 = \frac{R_f^2}{4c_1} \frac{(1-V_f)^3}{V_f^2} \quad \text{and} \quad K_2 = \frac{R_f^2}{4c_2} \frac{(1-V_f)^3}{V_f^2} \quad (8)$$

with the fibre radius R_f and the geometry constants c_1 and c_2 are then estimated from the porosity distribution applying the Kozeny-Carman approximation.

Fig. 7: Example for the values of V_f as functions of the co-ordinates x , y ; dimensions of the textile 500 mm \times 500 mm

Stochastic Simulations

Radial injection experiments were simulated for random distributions of a and b in a bi-directional non-crimp fabric. The main fibre orientations were assumed to coincide with the co-ordinate axes (Fig. 6). The equations describing the flow of a viscous liquid through a porous medium considering conservation of the fluid mass were solved based on a non-conforming finite element method [8], which is implemented in the PAM-RTM software. A value of 0.1 Pa·s was given for the viscosity η of the injected resin. The injection pressure Δp was set to 10^5 Pa. The number of fabric layers n , the cavity height h , the fibre density ρ , the superficial density S_0 , the Kozeny constants c_1 and c_2 and the fibre radius R_f were specified as listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Input parameters for calculation of local porosity and permeability values

n	h / m	$\rho / \text{kg/m}^3$	$S_0 / \text{kg/m}^2$	c_1	c_2	R_f / m
4	0.004	2600	0.936	0.017	0.040	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$

Random porosity and permeability distributions were generated for $R_p = 0.7$ mm and values of a_0 of 1.8 mm (global porosity 0.63) and 2.5 mm (global porosity 0.74). One set of values was assigned to each finite element by picking local values from the continuous functions by the co-ordinates of the centre of mass. For each value of a_0 and different fibre angle variations, a series of 20 injections at unsaturated flow was simulated and evaluated statistically. From the flow front propagation as a function of time, the isotropic global permeability k was determined for each series of simulations.

Results

The simulated flow front shapes indicate that the geometric scale of fabric inhomogeneities increases with increasing average fibre tow distance a_0 (Fig. 8). The results listed in Table 2 suggest that the ratio R_p/a_0 of in-plane fibre tow dimensions and average distance between the fibre tows, which characterises the fibre-void distribution in the fabric, affects both the average permeability values and the relative permeability variations (standard deviations / mean values). The permeability variations in general increase with decreasing R_p/a_0 . Nonetheless, due to the influence of the architecture on the permeability, different fabrics cannot be compared based on R_p/a_0 alone. The fibre angle variation σ_α imposes a boundary to the local variability in the textile structure.

Fig. 8: Examples for simulated flow front shapes; A: homogeneous material; B: $\sigma_\alpha = 20^\circ$, $a_0 = 1.8$ mm, $R_p = 0.7$ mm; C: $\sigma_\alpha = 20^\circ$, $a_0 = 2.5$ mm, $R_p = 0.7$ mm

Table 2: Mean values and standard deviations of k based on 20 simulations for each σ_α

σ_α	$k / 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$	
	$a_0 = 1.8 \text{ mm}, R_p = 0.7 \text{ mm}$	$a_0 = 2.5 \text{ mm}, R_p = 0.7 \text{ mm}$
0°	1.08	3.37
2°	1.39 ± 0.12 ($\pm 8.5 \%$)	1.63 ± 0.12 ($\pm 7.2 \%$)
5°	1.21 ± 0.21 ($\pm 17.1 \%$)	5.11 ± 0.83 ($\pm 16.2 \%$)
10°	1.08 ± 0.16 ($\pm 14.9 \%$)	4.34 ± 0.74 ($\pm 17.0 \%$)
15°	1.18 ± 0.14 ($\pm 11.8 \%$)	3.64 ± 0.90 ($\pm 24.6 \%$)
20°	1.07 ± 0.13 ($\pm 12.0 \%$)	3.54 ± 0.87 ($\pm 24.7 \%$)
30°	1.11 ± 0.12 ($\pm 10.8 \%$)	3.41 ± 0.65 ($\pm 19.0 \%$)
40°	1.10 ± 0.10 ($\pm 8.7 \%$)	3.55 ± 0.59 ($\pm 16.5 \%$)

To allow comparison of results for different R_p/a_0 , all global permeability variations are expressed as a function of the maximum frequency of fibre tow waviness. Since the global fibre volume fraction does significantly influence the permeability variations, all variations were converted to a fibre volume fraction of 56 %. The dependence of permeability variations on the fabric structure is characterised in Fig. 9. The global permeability variations increase with increasing maximum random frequency, until a maximum is reached at a critical frequency, which is related to the dimensions of the mould. For higher values of ω_{max} , the permeability variations decrease again. The higher the value of ω_{max} and the smaller the dimensions of the inhomogeneities, the more uniform the textile appears on a global scale and the lower are the permeability variations. It can also be concluded that the global permeability variation in general decreases with increasing mould dimensions.

Fig. 9: Relative permeability variations as a function of the maximum frequency of fibre tow waviness ω_{max}

CONCLUSIONS

To determine the local permeability of a reinforcement textile, resin flow is described at the unit cell level (meso-scale). The grid average method is based on spatial discretisation and local averaging of porosity and permeability of three-dimensional fibre tow arrangements on a regular grid. The local permeability is determined based on Darcy's law by imposing pressure boundary conditions on the boundaries of the computational domain and calculating the resulting flow rate. The procedure requires detailed geometrical modelling of the unit cell configuration, for which random effects, variations in the fibre angles, local compression of the fibre tows and variations in the fibre tow cross-section along the fibre axis may be considered. Application of the grid average method allows running large numbers of simulations, which is necessary to investigate the influence of different fibre angles on the permeability or to statistically evaluate flow through fibre configurations with randomised geometrical parameters. For the example of a 2x2 twill weave fabric, simulated permeability values as a function of the angles between fibre axes and the main flow direction show the same trend as observed experimentally. Since there are two concurrent mechanisms induced by fabric shear, the reorientation of the fibres relative to the flow direction, which causes either a reduction or an increase in permeability, and the reduction of porosity, which causes a reduction in permeability, the permeability has a maximum at a fibre angle for which the fibre axes are rotated towards the flow direction. Variation of the fibre configuration in the fabric unit cell, simulated based on a Monte-Carlo approach, results in normally distributed permeability values.

To determine the global fill time and the global flow patterns for manufacture of actual composite components, the resin flow is described at the component level (macro-scale). For shell-like components, two-dimensional flow is simulated, implying a homogenisation of the local fabric properties. The smallest level of homogenisation is based on the dimensions of the finite elements for the flow simulation, which usually include several textile unit cells. Material inherent variations of the local permeability are assumed to be mainly caused by stochastic variations in fibre spacing, which are described by spectral expansion of continuous random fields. Using the local fibre spacing, a porosity map is calculated. From the porosity, the principal permeability values are estimated locally based on the Kozeny-Carman equation. Since the randomised local properties are correlated in two dimensions, the approach is sound in terms of material continuity. Determination of the global flow behaviour is based on evaluation of simulations implementing the local permeability variations. For a bi-directional non-crimp fabric, resin injections were simulated for non-uniform reinforcement fabric properties. Based on statistical evaluation of the resulting flow front shapes, global permeability variations were determined. The permeability variations increase with increasing maximum frequency of fibre tow waviness until a maximum is reached at a critical frequency. For higher frequencies, the permeability variations decrease again. It is concluded that the smaller the dimensions of the fabric inhomogeneities, the lower are the global permeability variations, and that the global permeability variation in general decreases with increasing mould dimensions.

As the number of unit cells included in the meso-scale geometrical textile model for any fabric increases, the simulated flow is expected to converge to the global flow behaviour. However, due to limitations in computing power, detailed geometrical modelling of macro-scale components at the unit cell level for flow simulation is currently not possible. To describe macro-scale flow as accurately as possible, local geometrical fibre configurations can be generated for a component with given distributions of fibre angles and fibre spacings. The meso-scale analysis shows the potential for determination of local porosity and permeability

values for any fibre configuration, which can then be integrated into the global flow simulation.

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